

The Role of Academic Staff in Branding Tanzanian Universities: A Conceptual and Empirical Review

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Abstract:

The Tanzania's higher education sector has grown rapidly, from a handful public institutions at independence in 1961, to over 52 accredited universities by November 2025. This rapid growth has intensified the need to build distinctive, credible, and competitive institutional brands. While the literature on university branding has grown significantly over the past two decades, the role of academic staff as internal brand architects and external brand ambassadors remains underexplored, especially within Sub-Saharan Africa. This paper attempts to fill the gap in the Tanzanian context by undertaking a systematic conceptual review of the nexus between the internal branding theory, the employee-based brand equity and the unique operational realities of Tanzania's public and private universities. Drawing on the foundational brand equity frameworks, the emerging African higher education marketing literature, and the growing empirical university-branding research on Tanzania, the paper contends that the academic staff constitute a single most powerful yet most frequently neglected lever of university brand-building in Tanzania. Thus, it identifies the structural, cultural, and policy-related opportunities and challenges that shape academic staff brand engagement in this context and draws a framework and strategic recommendations for university leadership and policy makers to ponder.

Keywords: Academic Staff, Branding, Challenges, Rankings, Roles, Universities, Tanzania.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of branding, once confined to the commercial domain of fast-moving consumer goods and multinational corporations, has in the recent decades permeated the higher education sector remarkably. Globally, universities have increasingly embraced marketing philosophies, brand management practices and reputational strategies that were formerly the exclusive preserve of profit-oriented organizations (Chapleo, 2010; Hemsley-Brown & Goonawardana, 2007; Sujchaphong et al 2017). This shift has been driven by a confluence of forces: globalization, the massification of higher education, the intensification of competition for students, academic talent and research funding, and the increasing role of international university ranking as proxies for institutional quality (Kiraka et al 2020; Wæraas & Solbakk, 2009).

In Tanzania, these global trends have been amplified by a dramatic domestic expansion of the higher education sector. The country moved from just one public university at independence in 1961, the University of Dar es salaam, to 52 accredited universities by November 2025, comprising of 20 public and 32 private institutions Tanzania Commissions for Universities (TCU, 2026). This quantitative growth has created an intensely competitive landscape in which institutions must differentiate themselves not only to attract students, but also to recruit and retain qualified academic staff, secure funding partnerships, attract research collaborations, and build community trust. Despite this competitive imperative, most Tanzanian universities have approached branding as a primarily external and aesthetic exercise; investing in logos, marketing brochures, and social media pages, while neglecting the most fundamental brand-building resource they possess: their academic staff (Amani, 2023; Whisman, 2009).

The centering of academic staff in university branding is grounded in the distinctive nature of universities as organizations. Unlike product manufacturers, universities deliver highly intangible, human-intensive services in which credibility, expertise and conduct of academic staff are inseparable from the brand promise itself (Berry, 2000; Hemsley-Brown & Oplatka, 2006). When a prospective student evaluates a university, they are, in large part, evaluating the quality and reputation of its academic community. When research funders consider partnerships, they are assessing the intellectual capital embedded in its professoriate. When employers recruit graduates from a university, they are making a judgement about the values and competencies that its faculty has cultivated. In each of these brand touchpoints, academic staff are not merely supporting actors, they are the brand (Ind, 2007; Frandsen et al, 2018).

Despite this centrality, the internal branding of universities; the process of engaging, aligning and activating staff around the institutional brand remains underdeveloped in both practice and research, especially in the African context. Mogaji et al (2020a, 2020b), have documented the broader marketisation of African higher education. However for Tanzania, the specific mechanisms through which academic staff contribute to, or undermine university brand equity, have received limited systematic scholarly attention. The exceptions are notable: Amani's (2023) study provides empirical

evidence from a structural equation modelling involving 477 employees across Tanzania's public universities, which found that internal corporate social responsibility and psychological contract fulfilment significantly predict employee brand evangelism.

Similarly, Buzohera (2025) used a Partial Least Squares – Structural Equations Modelling (PLS-SEM) on 208 stakeholders across four Tanzanian institutions and found that social media marketing mediates relationships between brand building activities and institutional brand outcomes. However, no this study did not find any conceptual paper that has comprehensively synthesized the full landscape of academic brand roles within Tanzanian universities.

This paper has sought to fill this gap by addressing the following objectives,

1. To situate the Tanzanian education context within the global university branding literature
2. To develop a conceptual framework for understanding academic staff as internal brand architects and external brand ambassadors;
3. To identify the specific opportunities that Tanzania's higher education environment presents for leveraging academic staff in brand building; and
4. To document the structural, cultural and policy challenges that inhibit academic staff brand engagement in Tanzania, with strategic recommendation for overcoming them.

2. TANZANIA UNIVERSITIES: CONTEXT AND LANDSCAPE

2.1 Historical development

The history of higher education in Tanzania is, in many respects, a history of the state's ambition for national development. The University of Dar es salaam (UDSM), was established in 1961 as a constituent college of the University of East Africa. In 1970, it became a fully autonomous institution and served for decades as the sole public university in the country. Guided by Ujamaa (socialist) philosophy of Tanzania under President Julius Nyerere, the university was conceived as an institution in the service of national liberation and development, a philosophy that profoundly shaped the culture and self-conception of its academic community (Ishengoma, 2013; United Republic of Tanzania, 1999).

Significant liberalization of the higher education sector began in the 1990s following structural adjustment pressures and the enactment of enabling legislation, which encompassed the establishment of private universities, in addition to public ones. The university Act of 1992 and the subsequent National Higher Education Policy of 1999 (URT, 1999) provided the regulatory framework for what transpired into a proliferation of private universities, many of them with religious affiliations, throughout the 2000s and 2010s. By November 2025, TCU had approved 52 institutions of higher learning, 20 public and 32 private (TCU, 2026).

2.2 Structure and governance

The higher education sector in Tanzania is regulated and by the Tanzania Commission for Universities (TCU), which was established under the University Act No. 7 in 2005. TCU is responsible for the recognition, accreditation and quality assurance of all institutions of higher learning operating in Tanzania. The sector spans a diverse range of institutional types: comprehensive research universities, technical universities and faith-based universities.

Despite this diversity, the sector faces common structural challenges. Mgaiwa (2025) documents a persistent qualification gap within the Tanzanian academic profession, noting that only 26.4% of the total academic staff working Tanzania held doctoral degrees as of 2019. This figure is particularly important for the present discussion: if university brand equity is substantially a function of academic staff quality and reputation, then the low doctoral attainment level represents a structural constraint on Tanzania's capacity to build internationally competitive university brands. Mgaiwa and Ishengoma (2023) further document the challenge of chronic underfunding of public universities, reliance on student loan schemes, and the attendant pressure on academic working conditions; all of which have direct implications for academic staff identification with, and willingness to advocate for their institutional brands.

2.3 Competitive dynamics and rankings

The competitive dynamics of Tanzania's university sector have intensified as enrolment has grown and students have become more discerning consumers of higher education, influenced by global rankings, peer networks, social media and the perceived market returns to different degrees and institutions. The University of Dar es salaam has consistently maintained its position as Tanzania's most visible and internationally recognized university, ranking 32rd in Africa in 2025 quality rankings and first among all Tanzanian universities in Webometrics (UDSM, 2021; The Guardian Tanzania, 2025). The concentration, however, of national and international brand recognition of UDSM leaves the vast majority of Tanzania's 51 other institutions struggling for differentiated visibility, a context that makes effective marketing branding not a luxury, but a strategic imperative.

The competitive landscape has also been shaped by the increasing presence of international and regional universities operating in Tanzania, the growth of online and blended learning programmes (accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic), and the entry of foreign branch campuses such as Regency University (USA), Kampala International University (Uganda) and Joseph Business School (USA) to mention a few. The pressures have created what Mogaji et al (2020b) describe as a 'higher education market' dynamic in the African context, a market in which institutions must compete for students, staff and resources in ways that require genuine brand differentiation, not merely regulatory compliance.

2.4 Academic staff in the Tanzanian university context

Academic staff in Tanzanian universities operate within a complex web of institutional, cultural, professional and economic pressures. As documented by Mgaiwa (2025), the academic profession in Tanzania faces significant challenges including heavy teaching loads, insufficient research support, inadequate remuneration compared to remuneration in private sector companies and limited professional development opportunities. These conditions have contributed to what Mgaiwa terms as 'talent drain'. That is, the movement of qualified academics to better resourced institutions, international universities and the private sector.

On the other hand, Tanzanian academics occupy a position of considerable social and cultural prestige. In the Tanzanian social context, university lecturers and professors are widely regarded as authoritative figures, whose professional opinion and institutional affiliations carry significant social weight. This social capital represents an underutilized brand asset: when a Tanzanian academic publicly identifies with and advocates for their institutions, they communicate a signal of institutional quality to communities, families, potential students and employers that no marketing budget can easily replicate (Amani, 2023; Mogani et al, 2020)

3. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Theoretical foundation

This paper is grounded in three theoretical traditions that together provide a coherent framework for understanding the role of academic staff in university branding. The first is the brand equity tradition initiated by Aaker (1996) and Keller (1993), which conceptualizes brand value as a multi-dimensional asset comprising awareness, associations, perceived quality and loyalty. Applied to universities, brand equity represents the added value that an institution's name and reputation confer on its graduates, partners and stakeholders, value that is built, sustained, or eroded through the cumulative impressions created by every institutional touchpoint, including academic staff (Chapleo, 2010; Judson et al (2006).

The second tradition is the service brand management literature, where Berry's (2000) model of service brand equity is particularly instructive. Berry contends that in the service organizations, the company's primary brand is communicated not through products, but through the service experience delivered by frontline employees. Applied to universities, this means that the 'service encounter' between academic staff and students, community partners, and the external stakeholders is the primary arena of brand delivery. This contention makes academic staff not merely ambassadors of the predefined brand, but co-creators of the brand experience itself (Hemsley-Brown & Oplatka, 2006; Nguyen et al, 2016).

The third and most directly relevant theoretical tradition is internal branding (Burmann and Zeplin, 2005; Punjaisri and Wilson, 2007, 2009, King and Grace, 2009,

2010). Internal branding refers to the process through which organizations align employees' values, behaviours and identities with the brand promise, ensuring that employees not only understand the brand, but actively 'live' it in their daily professional conduct (Id, 2007; Phiehler et al, 2016). The key constructs of this tradition, brand knowledge, commitment, brand citizenship behaviour and employee-based brand equity, provide the conceptual vocabulary for analysing how Tanzanian universities can systematically develop their academic staff as brand assets.

3.2 Specific constructs applied to the Tanzanian context

Building on these three theoretical traditions, the present paper employs five specific constructs as analytical lenses.

Brand citizenship behaviour, defined by Burmann and Zeplin (2005) as voluntary performance of extra role behaviours that align with and strengthen the brand, is central to understanding what academic staff can contribute beyond their formal contractual obligations; for instance, public scholarship, media engagement, community outreach and active referral of prospective students.

Employee-based brand equity, as conceptualized by King & Grace (2009, 2010), refers to the brand relevant knowledge, skills and role clarity that employees possess, and their degree of identification with the brand. In the context of Tanzania universities, an academic staff member with high employee-based brand equity understands their institution's brand promise, can articulate it clearly to external stakeholders and behaves in ways that consistently reinforces it.

Brand evangelism, the concept employed by Amani (2022, 2023), refers to the passionate advocacy of a brand by a committed member of its community, in this case, an academic employee who proactively promotes their institution's brand beyond the boundaries of formal role, as a voluntary expression of identification and pride.

Employer branding, as theorized by Backhaus and Tikoo (2004), refers to the process through which an organization differentiates itself as an attractive employer. In the university context, this means that the brand experience of academic staff as employees, their working conditions; professional development opportunities, institutional culture and sense of belonging, directly shapes their willingness and capacity to function as brand ambassadors (Backhaus & Tikoo, 2004; Frandsen et al, 2018).

Internal corporate social responsibility (ICRS), as employed empirically by Amani (2023) in the Tanzanian context, refers to the institution's obligations to its employees; fair treatment, professional development, transparent communication and supportive working environment. Amani's (2023) structural equation model demonstrated that ICRS predicted psychological contract fulfilment, which in turn predicted employee brand evangelism, suggesting a clear and empirically validated mechanism through which Tanzania's university management can activate academic staff brand advocacy.

3.3 Methodology

This paper adopts a systematic conceptual review methodology (Torraco, 2005), whereby it synthesizes theoretical contributions and empirical findings from the global university branding literature, the African higher education marketing literature, and the emerging body of Tanzania-specific higher education and university branding research. The literature search drew on multiple electronic databases, including Scopus, Web of Science, Google Scholar, JSTOR, and the Routledge/Taylor & Francis Online platform, using search terms including ‘university branding,’ ‘higher education marketing,’ ‘internal branding universities,’ ‘academic staff brand,’ ‘Tanzania higher education,’ and ‘African university branding.’ Sources were selected based on their direct relevance to the research objectives, the credibility and currency of the publication outlet, and the quality of the methodological approach employed.

The paper’s analytical approach integrates deductive and inductive reasoning to draw implications from established theoretical frameworks for the Tanzanian context and to build empirical generalizations from the available Tanzania specific empirical evidence (Amani, 2021, 2022, 2023; Buzohera, 2025; Mgaiwa, 2025). The synthesis of these two models of reasoning produces a conceptual framework presented in section 4; that is grounded in theory, empirically informed and contextual sensitive.

4. WHAT ROLES CAN ACADEMIC STAFF PLAY IN BRANDING?

The first and most foundational role of academic staff in university branding is to function as architects of the brand experience from within an institution. As Whisman’s (2009) formulates the argument, internal branding is a university’s most valuable intangible asset. The point of departure is that a university brand is built from the inside out, not from the outside in; communications, values and culture that academic staff create within an institution inevitably permeate outward into every brand touchpoint, from the classroom experience of current students to the reputational signals received by employers, funders and peers in other institutions.

This inside-out perspective is particularly resonant in the Tanzanian context, where institutional marketing budgets are constrained and formal branding communication channels are underdeveloped. For most of Tanzanian universities, the primary communication that prospective students, families, and the wider community receive about an institution’s quality is not derived from advertising or rankings, but from the direct testimony of people who work there; academic staff whose professional lives are embedded in the local community and whose institutional affiliations are publicly known and socially meaningful (Amani, 2022; Mogaji et al, 2026).

Within an institution, academic staff shape brand experience through teaching quality, research productivity, curriculum relevance, student mentorship and the values they model in their daily professional conduct. Dean et al (2020) in their study of internal branding in a university rebrand, found that middle management academic staff; heads of departments and deans, played a disproportionately important role in mediating

between the institutional brand strategy and its practical implementation at the departmental level. This finding translates directly to the Tanzanian context: senior and experienced academic staff in departments, schools and faculties are effectively brand stewards, whose interpretation of the institutional brand determines how it is experienced by students, junior colleagues and community partners.

4.1 Academic staff as external ambassadors

Beyond their internal role, academic staff function as the primary external ambassadors of their institutions' brands in multiple overlapping communities. Frandsen et al (2018), in a discursive analysis of faculty responses to business school branding, documented the ways in which academic staff communicate institutional identity through their publications, public engagements, media appearances, conference presentations and professional networks; often more powerfully than any formal marketing activity. This observation is significant in the Tanzanian context, where academic staff frequently occupy visible public roles as commentators, advisers and community leaders.

Amani's (2023) empirical study of 477 employees from Tanzania public universities provides evidence of the brand evangelism phenomenon: academic employees who felt that their institution fulfilled its internal obligations to them (through ICDR and psychological contract fulfilment) were significantly more likely to voluntarily advocate for the institution to external stakeholders, recommend it as a place to study or work, and defend its reputation in public discourse. The findings are consistent with Burmann and Zeplin's (2025) and Punjaisri and Wilson (2007, 2009), both of which predict that when employees are effectively engaged with the brand, they proactively extend its reach into communities that no advertising campaign can access.

Academic staff brand ambassadorship in Tanzania takes several specific forms. Public scholarships; the translation of academic research into accessible public commentary for media, policy audiences and community forums, is perhaps the most visible. When an economist at the Catholic University of Mbeya appears on the national television to comment on monetary policy, or when a clinician at Muhimbili University advises the government on public health, they are communicating not only their own expertise but also the brand that their institution has produced, respectively, and hosts that expertise. Judson et al (2006), in their study of university brand building from within, found that such high-profile employee engagements had measurable positive effects on institutional brand perception, an effect that would be magnified in a context like Tanzania's, where media reach is high and institutional name recognition among public commentators is strong.

4.2 Academic staff and research reputation

Research reputation is, in many aspects, the cornerstone of a university brand on the global knowledge economy. Chapleo (2010, 2015) consistently identifies research quality and profile as one of the most powerful determinants of successful university brands,

Similarly, Hemsley-Brown and Goonawardana (2007) posit that brand harmonization in international higher education depends critically on the international visibility of institutional research output. For Tanzanian universities, research reputation represents both the greatest aspiration and the most acute challenge.

Research reputation is a structural challenge. Mgaiwa (2025) documents that the qualification gap, with only 26.4% of Tanzanian academic staff holding doctoral degrees, directly constrains research output, international publications, and research collaboration. Academic staff who do not hold doctoral qualifications are generally not well positioned to lead internationally peer-review research programmes, supervise doctoral candidates, or attract external research funding. These activities build brand equity in the international higher education market. A shortage of doctoral qualification generates a compounding effect; institutions with limited research-active staff struggle to build research reputations; without strong research reputations, they struggle to attract and retain the research-active academics who would build them. Breaking this cycle requires deliberate investment in academic staff development as a brand-building strategy.

Despite this challenge, there are institutions and individuals within Tanzania's university sector that demonstrate the transformative brand impact of research excellence. UDSM's position as Tanzania's most internationally recognized university is substantially built on the research reputation accumulated over decades by its academic staff. This premise is supported by Wæraas and Solbakk's (2009) observation that the 'essence' of a university brand is ultimately defined by its intellectual community, not its marketing department. The lesson for other Tanzanian institutions is that investment in academic staff qualification, research support and publication infrastructure is not merely a quality assurance matter, it is a brand investment with long term reputational returns.

4.3 Academic staff and student brand experience

Students are both the primary consumers of the university brand experience and upon graduation, its most numerous ambassadors. The quality of the student brand experience is determined overwhelmingly by the quality of the academic staff they encounter; in lectures, seminars, supervision sessions, conversations and myriad informal interactions that constitute university life. Amani (2023) in his study of internal branding and students' sense of belonging in Tanzanian universities found that students who experience strong institutional belonging and construct closely related to the quality of their academic relationships, were significantly more likely to intend to become active members of alumni associations, which are in turn key vehicles of post-graduation brand advocacy.

This finding has significant practical implications. It suggests that the student brand experience and its long-term ambassadorial consequences, are substantially produced by academic staff through their everyday conduct of teaching and mentorship. Berry's (2000) service brand equity model captures this dynamic precisely: in service organizations, the brand is made real through service delivery encounters and the consistency and quality of those encounters determine the long-term brand equity that

accumulates in the memories and testimonials of service recipients. For Tanzanian universities, the implication is that programmes aimed at improving teaching quality, student-staff relationships and academic pastoral support are simultaneously brand building investments, whose returns extend well beyond the graduation ceremony.

4.4 Academic staff identification and brand commitment

The effectiveness of academic staff as brand contributors depends critically on their degree of identification with commitment to the institutional brand. King and Grace's (2009, 2010) employee-based brand equity framework identifies three key conditions for strong brand commitment: brand knowledge (understanding what the brand stands for), role clarity (understanding how one's own role contributes to the brand) and brand commitment (an emotional attachment to the brand as part of one's professional identity). Applied to Tanzanian universities, this framework suggests that academic staff brand engagement requires active institutional investment in all three conditions.

In the Tanzanian context, brand knowledge is often limited to inadequate internal communication from senior management about institutional strategy and brand positioning. Amani (2023) found that psychological contract fulfilment, which includes expectations of transparent communication, professional recognition, and career development, was a significant predictor of brand evangelism, suggesting that when universities fail to communicate clearly with academic staff about their direction, values, and aspirations, they forfeit the brand advocacy potential of their academic community. This finding echoes Chapleo's (2007) identification of academic staff scepticism and weak internal communication as the principal barriers to university branding in UK institutions; barrier that are likely more pronounced in the Tanzanian context given institutional resources constraints.

Role clarity is also frequently lacking, as academic staff in Tanzania universities are rarely given explicit guidance on their brand-related responsibilities or the branding implications of their public professional conduct. Unlike academic staff in well-resourced international universities, who may receive media training, public engagement support and clear guidance on representing their institution, most Tanzanian academics receive no formal brand orientation and must navigate their institutional ambassadorial role through intuition and peer example (Frandsen et al, 2018; Judson et al, 2006).

Brand commitment, the deepest form of staff engagement is generated when academic staff feel proud of their institutions, aligned with its values, and confident in its future. Mogaji et al (2020a) argues that African universities need to invest actively in building internal cultures of pride and belonging; cultures that transform academic staff from passive employees into active institutional advocates. In Tanzania, the faith-based private universities that constitute a significant portion of the sector, including Catholic, Lutheran, Adventist and Pentecostal institutions, offer an interesting case study. Their academic staff may already possess a degree of value-alignment with the institution's

religious mission, which create a natural foundation for brand commitment, even where formal brand management processes are absent.

5. OPPORTUNITIES FOR LEVERAGING ACADEMIC STAFF IN UNIVERSITY BRANDING

5.1 Social media and digital platforms

The rapid growth of social media adoption in Tanzania; with Facebook penetration exceeding five million users and WhatsApp serving as a primary communication platform across all demographic groups, presents Tanzanian universities with an unprecedented opportunity to leverage academic staff digital presence for brand building. Buzohera (2025) demonstrates empirically that social media marketing mediates brand building outcomes for Tanzanian universities, whereas Mogaji et al (2020a) document the growing strategic importance of digital channels for African universities branding. Academic staff who are active, credible and substantive contributors to public digital discourse; publishing research commentary, engaging in professional debates, sharing institutional achievements, create what might be termed as ‘organic brand content’ whose credibility far exceeds that of formally produced institutional marketing material.

The opportunity here is amplified by the academic staff’s positioning as trusted voices in Tanzania’s information ecosystem. Unlike corporate brand advocates, whose commercial motivation are transparent to audiences, academic advocates are perceived as independent, expert and disinterested. These qualities make their institutional testimonials particularly persuasive. Amani’s (2022) social identity perspective on brand evangelism suggests that academic staff who strongly identify with their institution’s brand will naturally extend that advocacy into their social media presence, requiring only supportive institutional conditions (recognition, content support and explicit encouragement) rather than formal instructions.

5.2 Research dissemination and public scholarships

Tanzania’s vision 2050 development agenda and the government’s aspirations for a knowledge-based economy create an enabling environment in which academic expertise is actively sought by policymakers, industry and civil society. Universities that position their academic staff effectively as authoritative contributors to national policy conversations, through high quality research, credible public scholarships and consistent media engagement, stand to build significant brand equity as institutions whose knowledge creates real social value.

The opportunity is further enhanced by Tanzania’s membership in regional academic networks, such as the Inter-University Council for East Africa (IUCEA), the African Union’s Pan African University and bilateral research partnerships with European and North American institutions, which provide platforms for Tanzanian academic staff to build international reputational profiles that reflect positively on their home institutions. Chapleo (2015) identifies the international visibility of academic staff

as a key differentiator for university brands in the global market; for Tanzanian institutions seeking to attract international students, research partners and development funding, the international profile of their academic community is a brand asset of growing strategic importance.

5.3 Alumni networks and employer relations

Tanzanian universities' academic staff have natural connections to alumni networks, employer communities and professional associations, which can be leveraged for brand amplification. As documented by Amani (2021), students who experience strong institutional belonging through positive academic relationships are more likely to become active alumni advocates, creating a virtuous cycle in which engaged academic staff produce engaged students who become engaged alumni and reinforce the institutional brand in the labour market and broader society.

The opportunity to formalize these connections through structured alumni engagement programmes, industry advisory boards and employer partnership initiatives represents a relatively low-cost brand building strategy for Tanzanian universities. In this model, academic staff serve as a bridge between the institution and its external stakeholder communities, making use of their professional networks, research collaborations and consultancy relationships to bring external credibility and employer confidence back into the institution brand. Backhaus and Tikoo (2004) argue that employer branding, the cultivation of reputation as a desirable workplace, is closely linked with academic brand reputation, suggesting that universities that position themselves as attractive employers for qualified academic staff simultaneously strengthen their student recruitment brand.

5.4 Institutional character and mission alignment

A distinctive feature of Tanzania's private universities is that a high proportion of them are faith-based. These universities, founded and sustained by Catholic, Lutheran, Adventist, Pentecostal and Muslim communities possess a built-in basis for brand differentiation through their explicit value orientation and community embeddedness. Academic staff at these institutions who share and embody the institution's religious and ethical values represent a particularly potent form of brand ambassadors: their professional identity and their institutional identity are aligned at a level that goes beyond contractual employment.

Ind's (2007) concept of 'living the brand'; the idea that authentic brands are built when employees genuinely embody institutional values rather than performing them instrumentally, describes exactly the brand potential available to Tanzania's faith-based universities. King and Grace (2009) found that brand commitment was strongest when employees perceived their organization's values as genuinely aligned with their own. For Tanzania's Catholic, Lutheran Adventist and Muslim universities, this alignment is a strategic brand asset which, if properly cultivated through internal branding processes,

could generate stronger academic staff advocacy than can be achieved in institutions where the brand is experienced as merely an external marketing construct.

6. CHALLENGES IN ENGAGING ACADEMIC STAFF AS BRAND CONTRIBUTION

6.1 The academic freedom-branding tension

Perhaps the most fundamental challenge in engaging academic staff as university brand contributors is the potential conflict between brand management imperatives and the principles of academic freedom that are constitutive of the academic profession. Jevons (2006) identifies this tension as one of the primary reasons ‘universities represent a prime example of branding going wrong’: the centralized brand control that effective brand management requires is structurally at odds with the collegial autonomy that universities’ academic communities demand. In the Tanzanian context, where academic freedom has been established as a constitutional and institutional principle, however variably realized in practice, this tension gap specific institutional expressions.

Academic staff who are asked to represent their institution’s brand in public discourse may face genuine dilemmas when their expert judgement leads them to conclusions that conflict with the institution’s preferred public messaging. A public health academic whose research findings challenge government health policies or an economist whose analysis conflicts with government economic orthodoxy, may find that their institutional brand management obligation and their academic integrity obligations are in direct conflict. Wæraas and Solbakk (2009) argues that the resolution of this tension requires universities to develop brand identities that are capacious enough to accommodate the full range of their academic communities’ legitimate intellectual position, an approach that treats academic freedom as itself a brand differentiator rather than a brand threat.

6.2 Qualification gap and research capacity

The documented qualification gap in Tanzania’s academic profession, with fewer than 26.4% of academics holding doctoral degrees (Mgaiwa, 2025), represents a structural constraint on the brand building capacity of academic staff across multiple dimensions. Academic staff without doctoral qualifications are generally not well-positioned to engage in high impact research, international publications, conference participation and the kinds of expert public scholarship that build both individual and institutional reputational profiles. They are also less likely to attract research funding, international collaborations and the peer recognition that constitutes academic reputation in the global knowledge economy.

This qualification gap is, however, not a static constraint. Tanzanian universities that invest strategically in staff development, sponsoring doctoral programmes, supporting conference participation, funding research and creating protected time for scholarships, can over time transform the qualification profile of their academic communities in ways that generate compounding brand returns. Mgaiwa and

Ishengoma's (2023) research on financing higher education in Tanzania, identifies resource mobilization challenges at the system level, but also points to institutional agency: universities that prioritize staff development within their existing resource envelopes can begin building the academic capacity on which long term brand equity depends.

6.3 Inadequate internal branding infrastructure

Most Tanzanian universities lack internal branding infrastructure, systematic brand orientation for new staff, ongoing brand communication, staff recognition programmes, media training and public engagement support, which could enable academic staff to function effectively as brand contributors. This is not primarily a resource problem, even though resource constraints are there. Rather, it is fundamentally a conceptual problem. As Chapleo (2007) documents in the UK context, university leaders frequently fail to see internal brand engagement as a distinct and necessary management function, treating brand management as synonymous with external marketing rather than as a comprehensive institutional programme that begins with staff.

In Tanzania, this conceptual gap is compounded by the relative underdevelopment of professional communication functions within university administrations. Most Tanzanian universities do not have dedicated communication offices with the capacity to support academic staff in public engagement, media relations or branding aligned knowledge dissemination. Without this infrastructure, academic staff who are willing to contribute to the institutional brand lack the tools, guidance and recognition that would sustain them and amplify their contributions (Judson et al, 2006; Whisman, 2009).

6.4 Working conditions and psychological contract

Amani's (2023) empirical findings that psychological contract fulfilment mediates the relationship between institutional treatment of employees and employee brand evangelism has direct and sobering implications for a majority of Tanzanian universities. When academic staff feel that the institution has failed to honour its obligation to them, through inadequate remuneration, heavy teaching loads that crowd out research time, limited professional development, poor working facilities or opaque governance, they are not only less willing to advocate for the institution externally; they may actively undermine the institutional brand through negative word of mouth, social media expression of grievances or simple disengagement from any activity beyond their minimum contractual obligation.

Mgaiwa (2025) documents the systematic nature of these challenges in Tanzanian public universities, noting that heavy reliance on part-time academic staff, employed on insecure, lowly paying contracts that provide none of the professional development or institutional belonging that full-time employment creates, has become structurally embedded in public universities. Such staff, who constitute a significant portion of teaching delivery in many institutions, are unlikely to experience the psychological

contract fulfilment that Amani (2023) identifies as the prerequisite for brand evangelism. The brand implications of this staffing model are negative in the long term, even though the short-term cost implications appear positive: the institution saves on salaries, while eroding the social capital that its academic community represents.

6.5 Cultural and contextual factors

Tanzania's cultural context introduces specific nuances to the academic staff-brand relationship that are not fully captured by the predominantly Western theoretical frameworks from which the university branding literature emerges. The communal orientation of much Tanzanian social life, the high regard for institutional seniority and hierarchy and the social significance of professional affiliation all shape how academic staff experience and express their relationship with their institution's brand in ways that may differ from Western academic culture.

Specifically, the concept of 'face,' the social reputation and dignity associated with professional standing, has implication for academic staff brand advocacy in Tanzania. Academic staff who publicly advocate for an institution they perceive as not living up to its stated values risk their own reputational credibility. Conversely, academic staff who are publicly associated with a prestigious institution benefit from a halo effect, which compound their own professional reputation. This dynamic creates a reciprocal brand relationship: the institution's brand shapes academic staff's social capital and academic staff's conduct shapes the institution's brand. Managing this reciprocal relationship effectively requires cultural sensitivity and contextual adaptation of the internal branding models developed for the Western context (Mogaji et al, 2020).

7. TOWARDS A FRAMEWORK FOR LEVERAGING ACADEMIC STAFF AS BRAND ASSETS

Based on the foregoing analysis, this paper proposes a five-element framework for leveraging academic staff as brand assets in Tanzanian universities. This framework, which draws on the theoretical foundations reviewed in section 3 and the contextual analysis of sections 4, 5 and 6, is intended to be applicable across the full diversity of Tanzania's university sector; public and private, large and small, research intensive and teaching focused.

First, institutions should invest in systematic internal brand education as part of the academic staff induction and continuing professional development process. This means not simply communicating the institution's logo and tagline, but engaging academic staff in genuine dialogue about the institution's values, aspirations and explaining explicitly how each member of the academic community should contribute to realizing that brand through their professional conduct. Whisman (2009) argues that this kind of brand orientation is universities' 'most valuable intangible assets;' in the Tanzanian context, it represents the foundational step from which all other brand engagement flows.

Second, universities should implement structured public engagement programmes that equip and support academic staff in translating their research and expertise into accessible public scholarship. This includes media training, social media guidance, partnership with national and regional media outlets, and dedicated staff time for public engagement activities. The brand return on such investment can be substantial. Chapleo (2015) identifies academic staff public engagement as one of the most cost-effective brand building activities available to universities, particularly those that lack resources for expensive advertising campaigns.

Third, university leadership should audit and improve the conditions that generate psychological contract fulfilment among academic staff, addressing the working conditions, remunerations, professional development and governance transparency shortcomings that Amani (2023) and Mgaiwa (2025) identify as inhibitors of brand evangelism. This element positions staff welfare as a brand investment, not merely a human resources obligation. The empirical chain runs from ICSR to psychological contract fulfilment to brand evangelism. Amani (2023) provides a clear evidence-based rationale for institutional leadership to prioritize staff welfare as a reputational strategy.

Fourth, institutions should establish academic staff recognition and reward systems that explicitly value and acknowledge brand contribution behaviours, including public scholarships, media engagement, alumni relations, community outreach and student mentorship, along with traditional academic metrics of publications and grant success. King and Grace's (2010) employee-based brand equity framework identifies recognition and reward as a key determinant of brand commitment; in Tanzania context where academic recognition systems are often narrowly focused on traditional academic outputs, expanding the recognition framework to include brand-contributing behaviours could generate significant engagement dividends.

Fifth, Tanzanian universities should work with TCU and national education policy makers to develop sector-wide quality improvement initiatives that are geared at accelerating the filling of the qualification gap identified by Mgaiwa (2025). The goal, moving from the current 26.4% doctoral attainment rate to a rate closer to over 80% that characterizes leading African and international universities, requires a multi-decade commitment and significant public and institutional investment. But the brand implications of such an improvement would be transformative: a Tanzanian university sector populated predominantly by doctoral qualified, research active academics capable of contributing to international knowledge production would have fundamentally stronger brand equity than the current sector, regardless of any marketing investment.

8. CONCLUSION

This paper has advanced the premise, on the basis of a systematic conceptual review grounded in international branding theory and the emerging body of Tanzania-specific empirical evidence, that academic staff are the most powerful and most underutilized asset in the branding of Tanzanian universities. It has argued that while Tanzania is

rapidly expanding its higher education sector, now comprising 52 approved institutions, the universities are increasingly competing for students, staff, funding and reputational standing. Hence, they require genuine brand differentiation. The most credible and sustainable source of competitive brand advantage lies not in marketing budgets, digital campaigns, or logo redesigns, but in the intellectual capital, social networks, public engagement and daily professional conduct of academic communities.

The theoretical case for this position is compelling. Aaker (1996) and Keller's (1993) brand equity frameworks identify credibility and associations as core brand value drivers; in the context of a university, both are substantially created by academic staff. Berry's (2000) service brand model centres frontline employees as the primary brand delivery mechanism; in the university context, academic staff are the equivalency of frontline employees. Burmann and Zeplin's (2005) internal branding framework, and King and Grace's (2009, 2010) employee-based brand equity construct, provide both the conceptual architecture for understanding brand engagement and the practical levers; brand knowledge, role clarity, brand commitment, that institutions can deploy. Whisman's (2009) argument that internal branding is a university's 'most valuable intangible asset' crystallizes the argument most directly.

The empirical case is reinforced by Tanzania specific evidence. Amani (2023) study of 477 employees from Tanzanian public universities demonstrates the pathway from institutional treatment of staff to brand evangelism: institutions that fulfil their psychological contracts with academic staff produce brand advocates who voluntarily and passionately promote the institutional brand in their professional and social communities. Amani's (2022) social identity perspective on brand evangelism shows that this advocacy is driven by identification, academic staff who see their institutional identity as an integral part of their professional self are its most committed ambassadors. Buzohera's (2025) empirical work confirms that digital channels mediate brand building outcomes in the Tanzanian context, opening new avenues for amplifying academic staff brand contribution through social media and digital platforms.

The challenges documented in this paper, includes the academic freedom brand tension, the qualification shortfall, the inadequacy of internal branding infrastructure, the working conditions, the psychological contract failures, and the cultural contextual factors. However, these challenges are not, insurmountable. Each of them points to specific institutional actions and policy intervention that, if undertaken with strategic intentionality, would progressively unlock the brand potential of Tanzania's academic communities. The five-element framework has been proposed in section 7, which provide a structured starting point for this work. It includes covering brand education, public engagement support, staff welfare investment, recognition system reform and sector-wide qualification improvement.

The broader implication of this analysis extends beyond Tanzania. Across Sub-Saharan Africa, as the massification of higher education continues and competitive pressures intensify, universities face a fundamental issue of how to build credible and differentiated brands with resources available to them. The paper proposes the following

solution: invest in the academic community as a primary brand asset. This solution is not unique for Tanzania. It is a universal strategic fact about knowledge organizations whose brand are ultimately inseparable from the people who create and deliver the knowledge they promise. What is distinctive about the Tanzanian context is the specific configuration of opportunities and challenges that shape how this fact can be realized in practice.

Future research should build on the conceptual framework developed here through empirical investigation of academic staff brand engagement across a diverse sample of Tanzanian institutions; public and private, research intensive and teaching focused, urban and regional. Qualitative methods, such as in-depth interviews with academic staff, institutional administrators and students, would be particularly valuable in capturing the nuanced ways in which academic staff construct, negotiate and express their relationship with their institution's brand in the Tanzanian cultural context. Such research would both extend the Tanzania-specific empirical base and contribute to the broader theorization of academic staff brand roles in developing country higher education context.

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